

Consumer Attitudes and Perceptions of Online Banking in Pakistan: An Empirical Study

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Abstract

In recent times, the global banking sector has experienced a swift evolution. Enhanced information technology has improved commitment tracking and fulfillment, provided a variety of online customer service channels, and expedited problem resolution. This research employs a blend of theoretical models and quantitative methods to explore and confirm the statistical links between customer perceptions and attitudes regarding online banking. The primary aim of this empirical study is to identify and analyze key factors that shape customers' perceptions and attitudes towards online banking. These key factors have a positive influence on customer perception and attitude, with convenience being a significant element that greatly affects customers' perceptions and attitudes

Keywords: Customer Perceptions, Customer Attitude, Online banking factors.

Introduction

Banking technology in Pakistan, which was virtually non-existent until recent years, is now transforming how customers access and use banking services. Innovations like online banking, ATMs, and mobile banking have not only enhanced customer convenience but also reduced transaction costs for banks. Online banking platforms enable routine transactions such as transfers, balance inquiries, bill payments, stop-payment requests, and even processing loan and credit card applications. Customer Perception in Pakistan: Perceptions of online banking among Pakistani customers vary, influenced by demographic factors and overall satisfaction with the service. Ease of use and convenience are pivotal in altering customer perceptions. Perceptions about service quality and satisfaction are significantly shaped during direct service encounters. Shostack (1985) defines a service encounter as "a period of time during which a consumer directly interacts with a service." This interaction is key in influencing the adoption of internet banking as a preferred alternative.

Technology is a major driver of change in today's business world, fostering new products, services, and market opportunities. It has led to more information- and system-oriented business and management processes. Internet banking, a manifestation of this change, embodies the concept of banking anywhere, anytime. However, the growth of online banking is influenced by contradictory dynamics: the convenience of service and concerns about security. As highlighted by Benamati

and Serva (2007), and Jane et al. (2004), security, trust, and privacy are paramount for consumers considering online banking. Regular interaction with technology is necessary for consumers to maintain a level of comfort with e-banking services (Servon and Kaestner, 2008).

Consumer Concerns: Incidents of identity theft and data breaches increase consumer hesitation in conducting online financial transactions. Despite advancements in e-commerce, these concerns remain a barrier in the adoption of internet banking. This report examines the lingering reluctance among customers to embrace online banking despite the fall of many online commerce barriers. Understanding customers' attitudes and activities towards online banking is crucial for banks to launch and sustain these services successfully. Building customer loyalty involves addressing complaints effectively and ensuring protection against hacking and theft. Research indicates that several factors, including demographics, motivation, behavior towards banking technologies, and acceptance of new technology, shape consumer attitudes towards online banking. Prior experience with computers and technology also plays a role (Laforet and Li, 2005). A major issue in online banking is security. Addressing these concerns is essential for the growth and acceptance of online banking globally. As Chau and Lai (2003) note, attitude directly affects usage when intention is unclear.

This study aims to identify variables influencing customer perception and attitude towards online banking in Pakistan and to assess whether these influences are positive. The research questions include:

1. Does online banking influence customer perception and attitude?
2. Do risk factors positively influence customer perception and attitude?
3. Does the convenience factor positively influence customer perception and attitude?
4. Does the time factor positively influence customer perception and attitude?
5. Does the privacy factor positively influence customer perception and attitude?
6. Does the complexity factor positively influence customer perception and attitude?

This report is useful in identifying challenges and benefits associated with online banking, benefiting both banks and customers. It also assists banks in adopting new technologies and innovations to remain competitive and gain customer trust. The study's limitations include its methodology and application, as the survey method uses a convenience sample, which may not accurately represent the entire population. Additionally, the sample size is considered small.

Literature Review:

S. Arunkumar (2006) investigated the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and its efficacy in deciphering how user perceptions impact their motivation to adopt Internet Banking. TAM, rooted in Fishbein and Ajzen's Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA), posits that social behavior is driven by behavioral attitudes. It highlights four key factors - perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, and perceived enjoyment - as influential in shaping attitudes and intentions towards Internet Banking. Perceived usefulness is particularly critical as it reflects the belief in improved performance through Internet Banking usage. As users gain experience, perceived ease of use becomes more nuanced, influenced by their interactions across various contexts.

Karjaluoto et al. (2002) and Laforet and Li (2005) found that prior experience with technology and attitudes towards computers significantly affect both attitudes towards and actual use of online

banking. Davis (1989) emphasized the strong, consistent relationship between perceived usefulness and usage, outstripping other variables like attitudes or satisfaction measures. This highlights the direct impact of perceived usefulness on usage intentions, beyond its influence through attitude.

Gerrard and Cunningham (2003) noted that perceived usefulness also depends on the range of banking services offered, influencing adoption decisions. Dobdinga Cletus Fonchamnyo (2013) added that perceived reliability, trust, security, and accessibility significantly affect the perceived usefulness of e-banking adoption. Davis (1989, 1993) defined ease of use as the degree to which using technology is perceived to be effortless.

Arunkumar (2006) identified perceived ease of use as a crucial factor, suggesting that Internet Banking is seen as involving minimal effort. He also recognized perceived enjoyment (PE) as an intrinsic motivator in system use, finding a positive relationship between PE and attitudes towards Internet Banking. Various studies (Davis et al., 1992; Igbaria et al., 1995; Teo et al., 1999) have observed the significant impact of PE on the intention to use computers.

Regarding the practical aspects of Internet Banking, Karjaluoto et al. (2002), Turban et al. (2000), and Benamati and Serva (2007) highlighted its time and cost efficiency, convenience, and improved service response. Security, trust, and privacy emerged as critical concerns for online banking adoption.

Varsha Kuchara (2012), Divya Singhal et al. (2008), and S. Suriyamurthi et al. (2012) explored consumer perceptions, emphasizing the importance of security, convenience, and awareness programs in influencing attitudes towards Internet Banking. Sylvie Laforet et al. (2005) identified security as a key motivator in China, with concerns like hacking and fraud being major adoption barriers.

Further, demographic factors like age, education, and marital status (Dobdinga Cletus Fonchamnyo, 2013; Okey Peter Onyia et al., 2011) and variables like banking needs, service quality, and privacy concerns (Shah Ankit, 2011; Karjaluoto et al., 2002; Sumedha Kalia et al., 2012) have been found to significantly influence consumer attitudes and satisfaction with online banking.

Lastly, Nelson Oly Ndubisi et al. (2006) and Mohd Suki (2011) identified attitudinal factors like importance to banking needs, compatibility, complexity, and trialability as key predictors of Internet Banking adoption, underscoring the role of perceived risks and the need for a user-friendly, compatible system that aligns with customer needs and lifestyles.

Theoretical Framework:

Hypothesis 1: There is a positive correlation between customer perceptions and attitudes towards online banking and the risk factor. This hypothesis is based on the risk factor framework outlined in Shah Ankit's "Factors influencing online banking customer satisfaction and their importance in improving overall retention level" (Journal of Information and Knowledge Management, 2011), Nelson Oly Ndubisi et al.'s "Consumer attitudes system's characteristics and internet banking adoption in Malaysia" (Journal of Management Research News, 2006), and "Customer perception of e-banking adoption in Cameroon: An empirical assessment of an extended TAM" (International Journal of Economics and Finance, 2013).

Hypothesis 2: Customer perceptions and attitudes towards online banking positively correlate with the convenience factor. This is grounded in the findings from Shah Ankit's study in the Journal of Information and Knowledge Management (2011) and Sylvie Lafort et al.'s research on "Consumers' attitudes towards online and mobile banking in China." The convenience factor encompasses aspects such as anytime and anywhere access, no queues, time-saving compared to traditional banking, user-friendliness, and ease of use in e-banking transactions.

Hypothesis 3: There is a positive relationship between customer perceptions and attitudes towards online banking and the time factor. Influential studies include "Study on Customer Perception Towards Internet Banking: Identifying Major Contributing Factors" by Divya Singhal and V. Padhmanabhan (December 2008), and Beer (2006) and Srivastava (2006) who highlight time savings as a significant motivator for customers using internet banking.

Hypothesis 4: Customer perceptions and attitudes towards online banking are positively correlated with the privacy factor. This hypothesis is based on Shah Ankit's "Factors influencing online banking customer satisfaction and their importance in improving overall retention level" (Journal of Information and Knowledge Management, 2011), which examines various aspects of privacy such as the secure delivery of confidential information, information sharing with third parties, and customers' trust in the bank's privacy measures.

Hypothesis 5: There is a positive correlation between customer perceptions and attitudes towards online banking and the complexity factor. This is based on the findings in Nelson Oly Ndubisi et al.'s article "Consumer attitudes system's characteristics and internet banking adoption in Malaysia" (Journal of Management Research News, 2006), focusing on how the complexity of online banking systems affects customer adoption and usage.

Methodology:

The research employed a cross-sectional design, utilizing a correlational approach to explore the relationship between customer perception and attitude and online banking. A regression analysis was conducted to determine how customer perception and attitudes, along with factors like trust, risk, privacy, time, and complexity, contribute to online banking usage. This study was both descriptive, providing detailed information about these relationships, and analytical, examining the connections between different study variables.

Descriptive research, often referred to as Statistical Research, aims to describe characteristics and data about the subject under study. It typically involves analyzing frequencies, averages, and other statistical calculations. While this research approach is known for its accuracy, it doesn't explore the underlying causes of observed phenomena.

The study focused on customers with bank accounts who use online banking in the Lahore region. All such customers were invited to participate in the survey. The process of sampling involved selecting a subset of individuals from this larger population, ensuring that the sample represented the general population. The sampling methodology varied, including techniques like simple random sampling, systematic sampling, and observational sampling.

The sample size for the survey, conducted via questionnaires and mail, was 200. The study used non-probability sampling techniques. The questionnaire, designed based on previous empirical literature, served as the primary method for data collection. It included items relating to online banking and customer perceptions and attitudes, measured on a 5-point Likert scale (from 5 - strongly agree to 1 - strongly disagree).

Respondents were asked to express their level of agreement or importance regarding various aspects of online banking, using multiple items to ensure accurate measurement properties. The questionnaire's design was guided by literature, focusing on direct measures of customer perception and attitude influenced by various online banking factors.

The questionnaire was divided into four sections, beginning with demographic questions about gender, age, and qualification. The first section, based on Mohammed Ather Akhlaq's study (Journal of Internet Banking and Commerce, April 2011), focused on customer perception and attitude with 3 items. The second section, drawing from Mohammed Ather Akhlaq's study and Shah Ankit's research (Journal of Information and Knowledge Management, 2011), examined risk and convenience factors with 8 items. The third section assessed time and privacy factors with 7 items, influenced by Shah Ankit's study and Mwesigwa Rogers' research on Internet banking

adoption in Uganda. Finally, the fourth section, based on Nelson Oly Ndubisi's study, explored the complexity factor with 6 items.

Statistical analyses were conducted using the SPSS Software, with a detailed presentation of descriptive statistics in the data analysis section. The study began by examining bar charts and cross-tabulations of demographic variables, assessing the reliability and correlations among them. Additionally, the results of the regression analyses have been included in the data analysis section. The research model was formulated based on theoretical frameworks and observations of real-world phenomena. A comprehensive summary of all the proposed hypotheses is also provided in the study.

The reliability or internal consistency of a measure is gauged by its degree of consistency. To evaluate the reliability of a scale, the commonly used metric is Cronbach's alpha (Cronbach, 1951). A Cronbach's alpha value of 0.70 or higher is considered to represent good scale reliability (O'Leary-Kelly and Vokurka, 1998). In this study, the Cronbach's alpha values for the six factors are approximately 0.70, indicating that they all demonstrate reliable measurement.

		Qualification					
		Bachelor's					
		secondary	diploma	degree	Masters	PHD	Total
gender	female	1	6	28	31	3	69
	male	5	9	65	41	11	131
Total		6	15	93	72	14	200

Table 1

The chart illustrates a comparison between gender and educational qualifications among online banking users. It reveals that a mere 1% of female users possess secondary education, while 6% hold a diploma. Females with a bachelor's degree constitute 28%, and those with a master's degree account for 31%, a figure that is higher compared to other female groups but lower than their male counterparts holding master's degrees. Only 3% of the female users are in the PhD category.

In contrast, the proportion of male users engaging in online banking is greater. Among them, 5% have completed secondary education, and 9% have diplomas, surpassing the female percentage. A significant 65% of the male respondents have a bachelor's degree, the highest ratio observed. Additionally, 41% of these male users possess a master's degree, and the remaining 11% have PhDs. This data suggests that online banking is predominantly utilized by males, particularly those with higher education levels.

Regression analysis

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.548 ^a	.300	.282	.64314

a. Predictors: (Constant), complexity factor, time factor , convenience factor, Risk factor, privacy

Table 2

ANOVA ^b						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	34.445	5	6.889	16.655	.000 ^a
	Residual	80.244	194	.414		
	Total	114.689	199			

a. Predictors: (Constant), complexity factor, time factor , convenience factor, Risk factor, privacy

b. Dependent Variable: customer perception attitude of online banking

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.603	.394		1.530	.128
	Risk factor	.072	.077	.064	.944	.347
	convenience factor	.422	.073	.391	5.821	.000
	time factor	.062	.053	.078	1.160	.247
	privacy	.067	.077	.060	.875	.383
	complexity factor	.238	.096	.166	2.481	.014

a. Dependent Variable: customer perception attitude of online banking

Regression analysis is employed to forecast a dependent variable based on one or more independent variables. This involves creating a mathematical formula:

$$Y=a+b_1X_1+b_2X_2+b_3X_3+b_4X_4+b_5X_5$$

Here, (Y) represents the dependent variable, which in this context is customer perception and attitude towards online banking. (X1, X2, X3, X4,) and (X5) are independent variables representing risk, convenience, time, privacy, and complexity, respectively. The coefficients (b1, b2, b3, b4,) and (b5) quantify the impact these independent variables have on (Y), while (a) indicates the predicted value of (Y) when all independent variables are zero.

The derived equation is:

$$Y=0.603+0.072X_1+0.422X_2+0.062X_3+0.067X_4+0.238X_5$$

Breaking down the equation, the convenience factor (X2) shows the highest value at 42.2%, indicating a significant influence on customer perception and attitude. This suggests that users appreciate the speed and ease of online banking transactions. The complexity factor (X5) at 23.8% also has a considerable impact, albeit less than convenience. The risk factor (X1) at 7.2% has a lesser influence compared to convenience and complexity but more than time and privacy factors, which are at 6.2% and 6.7% respectively.

The R-square value of the regression is 30%, revealing the proportion of variance in the dependent variable explained by the independent variables. The adjusted R-square is 28.2%, indicating a minor difference (1.80%) in variance prediction if the study were conducted on the entire population rather than a sample. This aligns with Shah Ankit's (2011) study, where about 37.4% of the outcome variability was accounted for by the predictors.

The F statistic value is 16.655 with a p-value of 0.000, signifying a significant impact of the independent variables on the dependent variable at a 5% significance level, confirming the model's effectiveness. The absence of multicollinearity is confirmed by collinearity diagnostics. Dobdinga Cletus Fonchamnyo's study also highlighted that customer attitude significantly influences e-banking adoption, accounting for 16.6% of the variation, with a positive coefficient of 0.249, indicating that higher customer attitude towards adoption correlates with increased likelihood of adopting e-banking.

Correlation analysis

		<u>Correlations</u>					
		customer perception attitude of online banking	Risk factor	convenience factor	time factor	privacy	complexity factor
customer perception attitude of online banking	Pearson Correlation	1	.244**	.491**	.212**	.298**	.351**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.003	.000	.000
	N	200	200	200	200	200	200
Risk factor	Pearson Correlation	.244**	1	.212**	.382**	.329**	.286**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.003	.000	.000	.000
	N	200	200	200	200	200	200
convenience factor	Pearson Correlation	.491**	.212**	1	.117	.375**	.329**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.003		.099	.000	.000
	N	200	200	200	200	200	200
time factor	Pearson Correlation	.212**	.382**	.117	1	.305**	.273**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.003	.000	.099		.000	.000
	N	200	200	200	200	200	200
privacy	Pearson Correlation	.298**	.329**	.375**	.305**	1	.279**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	200	200	200	200	200	200
complexity factor	Pearson Correlation	.351**	.286**	.329**	.273**	.279**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	200	200	200	200	200	200

Interpretation of correlation analysis:

The Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (r), or simply the correlation coefficient, is a metric that quantifies the degree of linear relationship between two variables, typically denoted as X and Y. Unlike regression, which focuses on predicting one variable from another, correlation

emphasizes the extent to which a linear model can represent the relationship between two variables. In correlation analysis, the direction of the relationship is not emphasized; rather, the existence and strength of the relationship are of primary interest. The correlation coefficient ranges between -1 and +1.

The sign of the correlation coefficient (+ or -) indicates the direction of the relationship. A positive correlation means that as one variable increases, the other also increases, and similarly, they decrease together. Conversely, a negative correlation suggests that as one variable increases, the other decreases, and vice versa.

In this study, the correlation coefficient reveals a strong association between the dependent variables (customer perception and attitude) and the independent variables, as evidenced by the following hypotheses:

(H1): Customer perception and attitude towards online banking is positively correlated with the risk factor. The correlation coefficient for the risk factor is 0.244, indicating a positive relationship at the 5% significance level. This suggests a significant influence of the risk factor on customer perception and attitude, leading to the rejection of H0.

(H2): Customer perception and attitude towards online banking is positively correlated with the convenience factor. The correlation coefficient for the convenience factor is 49.1%, signifying a strong relationship with customer perception and attitude.

(H3): Customer perception and attitude towards online banking is positively correlated with the time factor. The correlation coefficient for the time factor is 21.2%, indicating a positive influence on customer perception and attitude.

(H4): Customer perception and attitude towards online banking is positively correlated with the privacy factor. The correlation coefficient for the privacy factor is 29.8%, showing a direct correlation with customer perception and attitude.

(H5): Customer perception and attitude towards online banking is positively correlated with the complexity factor.

The correlation coefficient for the complexity factor is 35.1%, indicating a positive relationship.

Discussion and findings

The model empirically posits that factors related to online banking functionality have a positive impact on customer perception and attitude. Furthermore, it suggests that the influence of these factors varies according to personal characteristics such as gender, age, and educational level. Observationally, 65.5% of online banking users are male, surpassing female users. The primary user demographic falls within the 20-40 age range, expressing satisfaction with online banking transactions, while usage in those above 40 is relatively lower. Online banking adoption also correlates with users' familiarity with the system, often influenced by their educational level and knowledge.

The model's R-square value stands at 30%, indicating that a significant portion of the variance in the dependent variable (customer perception and attitude) is explained by independent variables like risk, convenience, time, privacy, and complexity. Additionally, Dobdinga Cletus Fonchamnyo's research highlights that customer attitude significantly impacts e-banking adoption, accounting for 16.6% of the variance in adoption rates. A positive correlation is observed, where a higher customer attitude towards e-banking adoption correlates with increased likelihood of adoption, as evidenced by a coefficient of 0.249.

In the correlation analysis, all variables are significant at the 0.05% level, leading to the rejection of all null hypotheses due to a positive and direct relationship between dependent and independent variables. Notably, the correlation between customer perception and attitude, and the convenience factor is around 50%. This indicates that customers prioritize convenience in online transactions, finding online banking efficient, user-friendly, and conducive to managing their financial needs. This finding aligns with Shah Ankit's study, which underscored the importance of convenience, significantly influencing customer satisfaction in online banking.

Following convenience, the complexity factor, with a ratio of 35%, also significantly influences customer perception and attitude. Some respondents highlighted the ease of conducting banking transactions and the simplicity of remembering ATM passwords. Nelson Oly Ndubisi's research also supports this, suggesting that internet banking is perceived as less complex and requires minimal mental and physical effort. Privacy concerns are evident among online banking users, with a 29.8% correlation indicating a strong relationship between privacy concerns and customer perception and attitude. Users express confidence in the privacy measures of online banking, trusting that their personal information is not shared without consent.

The risk factor, with a 24.4% correlation, suggests a positive attitude towards perceived risks in online banking, as users trust the security measures implemented by banks. Lastly, the time factor, with a 21.2% correlation, indicates a positive relationship, albeit weaker than other factors, with users finding online banking time-efficient and easy to learn.

Overall, while these factors significantly influence customer perception and attitude, it's clear that other factors also play a role in shaping user experiences and attitudes towards online banking.

Conclusions:

This study on the use and impact of online banking reveals significant insights into customer perceptions and attitudes. Key factors such as convenience, simplicity, privacy, perceived risk, and time efficiency are pivotal in shaping users' attitudes towards digital banking platforms. A notable preference for convenient, quick, and easily navigable banking services is apparent among most users. Simplicity in operations and robust privacy measures are also highly valued, reflecting a growing reliance on and confidence in the security protocols of online banking. This research also sheds light on how demographic factors like age, gender, and education level play a significant role in determining the adoption and perception of online banking services.

The increasing preference for digital banking solutions, especially among younger and more educated demographics, points to a digital shift in banking. However, a portion of the population remains either uninformed or apprehensive about these services, highlighting the necessity for more approachable and user-centric online banking platforms.

Implications:

The findings of this research carry substantial implications for the banking sector and financial institutions. Primarily, there is an urgent need for banks to further refine their online services, emphasizing ease of use and security to meet the evolving demands and concerns of their clientele. Investing in technologies that streamline operations and bolster security is critical for building user trust and confidence.

Equally important is the aspect of customer education. Banks must undertake extensive initiatives

to enlighten their customers about the advantages and functionalities of online banking, dispelling prevalent myths and addressing security worries. Such initiatives are especially crucial for engaging with the older, less tech-savvy demographic who may be reluctant to transition to online banking.

Moreover, this study highlights the significance of tailoring banking experiences to individual needs. Banks are encouraged to recognize and cater to the varied requirements of diverse demographic segments, ensuring that their services are attractive and accessible to all, irrespective of age, educational background, or tech-savviness.

Recommendations:

To enhance customer satisfaction and foster enduring relationships, it is crucial for banks to ensure the secure delivery of confidential information to customers and to maintain trust in their privacy protection measures. Banks should focus on upgrading their online banking technology. This improvement is not just about attracting more users to online banking platforms, but also about making these platforms more accessible and user-friendly. Advanced technology can help in simplifying processes and making transactions more secure, which in turn boosts user confidence and satisfaction.

Lowering the service charges associated with online banking transactions can be a significant motivator for customers. By making these services more affordable, banks can encourage a higher volume of transactions through online channels, including ATMs. This approach can be particularly effective in attracting customers who are cost-conscious or those who may be hesitant to use online services due to additional fees.

It is essential for banks to focus on the usability of their online banking systems. This involves removing complexities and making the system intuitive even for those who are not technologically savvy. Simplifying the online banking experience can help in breaking down barriers to adoption, especially among users who may be resistant to new technologies.

Banks should also invest in educational initiatives that help customers understand and use online banking services effectively. This could involve user guides, tutorials, and customer support designed to assist users in navigating the online banking environment. By educating customers, banks can help them make the most of the available facilities and services, thereby improving their overall banking experience.

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